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Importance of Gender Equality to Empower Women in Indian Society

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Abstract:

In order to discuss regarding importance of gender equality to empower women in Indian society, it is very necessary for us to get a clear idea regarding gender equality and women empowerment. Gender equality means equal enjoyment of social, cultural and economic opportunities, attributes, rewards and resources by women and men. The process which helps women to empower themselves by gaining power, acquiring the ability to make strategic choices and achieving their right to bring about social change for themselves and others, is known as women empowerment. In India, gender equality is essential to empower women for the development of nation from all perspectives. In India, the focus on the education of girls plays a vital role to empower women by breaking down barriers, unlocking opportunities, sharing equality in the distribution of power and influence and fostering critical thinking. Without gender equality, it is not possible for women to get easy access to social, economic and cultural resources. But gender equality has the power of making women more powerful to redress imbalances. Women's empowerment must ensure their decision-making power at private and public levels and equal access to opportunities and life changes. For a more peaceful, prosperous and equitable nation, gender equality is very important in Indian society to empower women. It ensures women to access each and every opportunity. Empowering women through gender equality enables nation to improve social well-being, economic growth, and sustainable development; increase stronger communities, equality, better health, education and political participation; and reduce violence. The constitution of India has made several provisions in favour of gender equality to empower women through Fundamental Rights, Directive Principles of State Policies and other provisions for the overall development of India. Indian law along with Indian Constitution has taken an active part to provide gender equality to empower women in India.

Keywords: Gender, Equality, Empowerment, Development, Opportunity.

1. Introduction:

In order to discuss regarding importance of gender equality to empower women in Indian society, it is very necessary for us to get a clear idea regarding gender equality and women empowerment. Gender equality means equal enjoyment of social, cultural and economic

opportunities, attributes, rewards and resources by women and men. Gender equality can provide the chance of empowering women and girls to focus collaboration and investment for achieving long term, short term and medium-term benefits in the field of education, sanitation and nutrition. In India, gender equality is very important for social, cultural and economic upliftment and sustainable development of the country. But in India, [census 2011](#) has shown us how gender inequality affects the development of India.¹ The pathetic picture of child sex ratio from 0 to 6 years such as 918 girls per 1000 boys indicates efficient and urgent solution in favour of gender equality.

In Indian society, sometimes girl child is not allowed to be borne by the family to consider girl child as a burden. Although the Constitution of India includes [Article 14](#), [Article 15¹\(1\)](#), [Article 15\(3\)](#), [Article 16](#), [Article 21](#), [Article 23](#) of Fundamental Rights; [Article 39](#), [Article 42](#), [Article 44](#), [Article 45](#) of Directive Principal of State Policies; [Article 51 A](#), [51 A](#) of Fundamental Duties; and [Article 243D](#), [Article 243T](#) of Other Constitutional Provisions along with [Article 239AA](#), [Article 330A](#) and [Article 332A](#) of Nari Shakti Vandan Adhiniyan ([Women's Resevation Act](#)) 2023² to support gender equality and women's empowerment but the girl child is often deprived by the family and society from childhood of enjoying equal opportunities and basic rights. Sometimes violence, early marriage, sexual abuse, exploitation and domestic work prevent the girl from completing the journey of life. Only gender equality can help women to empower themselves for the overall development of India. Indian law along with Indian Constitution has taken an active part to provide gender equality to empower women in India.

2. Review of Literature:

Amitabh Singh has identified in his research in 2011 that gender inequality on account of female feticide and uneven sex ratio is the cause of giving rise to serious social issues such as prostitution, rapes, homosexuality, molestations and growth of polyandry which prevent society from moving towards prosperity. According to Dhruva [Hazarika \(2011\)](#)³, the harassment and discrimination of women is found in the Indian society till date in spite of respectable position occupied by the modern women in different walks of life. Her research work points out the necessity of promoting the gender equality for women empowerment in modern Indian society for the proper development of India. [Viney Kapoor, \(2011\)](#) points out the need of women's

¹ResearchGate, (PDF) Child sex ratio -declining trend: Reasons and ...; <https://www.researchgate.net> › ... › [Sex Ratio](#)

²BYJU'S, Directive Principles of State Policy (DPSP); <https://byjus.com> › free-ias-prep › directive-principles-

³ResearchGate,31 Dec 2024,(PDF) Women Empowerment: A Literature Review; <https://www.researchgate.net> › publication › 37124324...

proprietary rights for their economic independence, their social status, prosperous and dignified life, and individual security. By conceptualizing the violations of certain gender specific human rights particularly in the North East India, Jogesh Das, (2012)⁴ puts emphasis on the importance of making Human Rights of girl child and women as an integral part of the universal human rights to pay attention to World Conference on Human Rights in 1993. The least gender discrimination is found in the emergence of Information Technology as a powerful employment opportunity for women becoming suitable for their job environment as per analysis of Asmita Bhattacharyya and Dr. Bhola Nath Ghosh in 2012. They tried their level best to analyze the source of women empowerment in India from the opportunities and constraints faced by the women employees in the Information Technology Sector in India.

3. Research Gap:

My research topic is “Importance of Gender Equality to Empower Women in Indian Society”. Previous Records of research revealed that many works were conducted on different aspects of gender equality and women empowerment. But this is an important area which is untouched. Extensive research work is required. Hence there is a research gap. I have selected this topic for filling up this gap. As a result, my work explores new perspectives in this area.

4. Immersion of the problem:

4.1 Aim: The aim of this study is to point out the difficulties of gender equality to empower women in Indian society.

4.2 Objectives:

The following objectives are laid down for this study:

- (i) To investigate about social position of gender equality to empower women.
- (ii) To separate the problematized opinions regarding gender equality to empower women.
- (iii) To evaluate the role of gender equality to empower women in Indian society.
- (iv) To elucidate about the power of gender equality to empower women in Indian Society.
- (v) To illustrate the chronicles of gender equality to empower women to become powerful from powerlessness.

4.3 Rationale of the Study:

The path of gender equality to empower women in Indian society is a long journey of depression, strife and hope. For the development and progress of India, gender equality to empower women

⁴ Shodhgangotri, Literature Review; <https://shodhgangotri.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream>

in Indian society is very important. As a result, women empowerment inspires women to take part in social, political, economic and cultural spheres for the improvement of society. Gender equality to empower women provides a more prosperous society by unlocking the full potential of women. It increases women's sense of self-worth, helps them to determine choices, enjoy opportunities and resources, influence the direction of social change for creating a more improved social and economic order, and control their own lives both outside the home and within the home. For women empowerment, gender equality is the first and foremost necessary thing. Both of them is intertwined and interrelated to each other. Women empowerment is necessitated inherently by the pursuit of gender equality.

5. Methodology:

Methodology indicates the systematic, theoretical analysis of the method applied to a field of study. This paper written for International Journal has undertaken the study through an examination of primary source including quantitative data and secondary source related to the effect of gender equality to empower women in Indian society. The research methodology followed here is the theoretical frame and concept of gender equality to empower women in Indian society on the basis of primary data collected from Interviews and Survey, and secondary data where data were collected from newspapers, magazines, articles, websites, correspondence and documentary sources. The major concern of this writing is to highlight the necessity of gender equality to empower women in Indian society. This writing wants to point out the multifaceted aspects of gender equality to empower women in Indian society by highlighting different types of programmes of women empowerment in India in order to show the need of building gender-equal India to empower women.

6. Study Conducted:

In Ancient- Medieval India, many female deities like Durga, Kali, Saraswati and Lakshmi were worshipped in Indian society. Although patriarchal system was introduced since the Vedic Period. Indian history was enriched with the names of many marvelous women like Gargi, Maitreyi and Sulabha, who were famous for their excellent reasoning power; and many female rulers like Rani Durgavati and Prabhavati Gupta. In spite of it, women had to suffer silently for want of gender equality in Indian society since ancient times. In Pre-Independence India, the beginning of Socio-Religious Reforms Movements⁶ in 19th Century had supported gender equality to empower women in India. Raja Rammohan Roy, Swami Dayananda Saraswati, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar and the organizations related to them had come forward to promote gender equality to empower women in India. As a result, Sati Abolition Act of 1829, Widow Remarriage Act of 1856, Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929 were introduced to empower women.

Women's Organizations like Bharat Mahila Parishad, All India Women's Conference, and Women's Indian Association, were set up in the early 20th century onwards on the basis of demand for women's rights. They claimed women's right to vote, inheritance rights and other rights by pointing out gender inequality in India. Gandhiji encouraged women to participate in Indian Freedom struggle to fight for their political and social rights along with political freedom. This participation of women in national movements promoted women's empowerment and gender equality in India by empowering women with a sense of self-confidence to break away several barriers of old traditions.

In post- Independence India, the involvement of women activists in tasks of nation- building and trauma of partition raised gender parity movement to empower women for bringing India's independence. In India, Self Employed Women's Association and Annapurna Mahila Mandal came forward to empower women as the second phase of the Indian women's movement and gender equality movement in 1970s. Recently, various women's empowerment programs are launched by the Indian Government to promote gender equality to empower women⁵.

7. Data Collection:

Interviews and Survey through Questionnaire prepared by me were the process to collect information regarding *gender equality to empower women in India as Primary Sources*. I have collected data from secondary sources; i.e., newspapers, magazines, articles, websites, correspondence and documentary sources. Following Research Questions helped for designing the Questionnaire, on which basis survey was conducted.

- (i) What is gender equality?
- (ii) What is the relation between gender equality and women empowerment?
- (iii) How is the present condition of gender equality and women empowerment?
- (iv) Does gender inequality affect women's empowerment?
- (v) How is it possible for Indian women to enjoy gender equality to empower themselves?

The above questions have helped me to get a clear idea regarding gender equality to empower women.

8. Analysis of Collected Data:

The Survey Report collected from some women on the basis of Questionnaire on gender equality to empower women, has helped me to conclude my topic properly. Forty women belonging to age group between thirty years to fifty years have encouraged me by pointing out that my topic is very relevant in the context of present age. Data Analysis has added a new feather to my

⁵ NEXT IAS, 25 August 2025, Women Empowerment and Gender Equality in India: <https://www.nextias.com>
»Home» Indian Society

knowledge of qualitative and quantitative Methodologies. At the time of taking Interview, the different types of language functions like Listening, Enquiring, Explaining, Requesting and Note taking have helped this study to proceed. The four language skills like Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing have spread their hands to complete the Interview process.

On the basis of Data collection, it is possible for me to come to know about present condition of gender equality to empower women. Although some improvements have been taken place in the condition of women yet women in India have to face discrimination still now. Even today, Women are forced to play their traditional roles such as daughters, wives, mothers and mother-in-law to depend completely on their male counterparts on account of patriarchal mindset and gender inequality in India⁷.

The data analysis has revealed two opposite views regarding the present Indian society. Natural gender disparity based on the genetic or biological differences between men and women; and artificial gender disparity based on culture and social position play an important part to create gender inequality. At present, women in India have to face ongoing challenges and a complex interplay of progress along with important achievements in the field of gender equality to empower women. The data analysis has given an account regarding the present status of gender inequality based on Overall Disparity like overall gender gap; Socio-Cultural Disparity like sex ratio, malnutrition, education, child marriage as per the survey of NFHS (National Family Health Survey- 5, 2019-21), maternal mortality rate as per the special Bulletin on MMR, and gender-based violence; Economic Disparity like employment, informalization and Wage gap; and Political Disparity like representation in Parliament, representation in State Legislatures, representation in Local Panchayats. Attaining gender equality to empower women is a challenge based on Socio-cultural factors like Discriminatory Social Norms, Low Literacy, Safety Concerns, and Role Stereotyping; Economic factors like Economic Disparities, Glass Ceiling, and Lesser Employment Opportunities; and Political factors like Low⁶ Political Representation, and 'Sarpanch- Pati' Culture; and other factors like Inadequate Implementation of Laws, and Emerging challenges.

8. Findings:

On the basis of data analysis, it is possible to find out some processes of achieving gender equality to empower women in India. Laws related to protection of women's right must be strengthened and implemented properly to empower women. Women must be ensured to enjoy equal opportunities in the field of education and employment. Women must be

⁶ PWOnlyIAS, [Distinguish Between Gender Equality, Gender Equity And ...](https://pwnonlyias.com/pyq/distinguish-between-gen...):
<https://pwnonlyias.com/pyq/distinguish-between-gen...>

encouraged to take part in leadership roles in every walk of life. Creation of inclusive policies must be implemented to empower women for facing problems in society.

9. Conclusion:

Gender equality to empower women is very important. It is a fundamental human right as per opinion of United States. The overall importance of Gender equality to empower women is that it would improve the cause of social justice, national progress, peaceful society, better health, promotion of education, social change, social inclusion, economic development, workforce participation, increased innovations, better decision-making, and better outcome. Indian law along with Indian Constitution has taken an active part to provide gender equality to empower women in India. Gender equality for Socio-Cultural Empowerment of women like Indian Penal Code (IPC), Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987, Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, and Prohibition of Child Marriage Act; Economic Empowerment for women like Minimum Wages Act, 1948, Maternity Benefit Act, 1961, Equal Remuneration Act, 1976, and Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013; and Political Empowerment for Women like Representation of the People Act, 1950, and Delimitation Commission Act, 2002. At present, the attempts of gender equality to empower women in India play a significant role to the development of nation by helping economic growth; increasing the decision-making power of women in every step of life; inspiring them to take part in education, entrepreneurship, household income, national productivity, leadership for positive change and social reform; and encouraging them to uplift entire communities. Only continuous efforts can achieve to promote gender equality to empower women by removing disparities.

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